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Service Quality And Customer Satisfaction With Selected Hotels In Anambra State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influence of service quality on customer satisfaction with selected hotels in Anambra State. The reality is that hotel service providers face the challenges of attracting and retaining customers support based on the hospitality environment which necessitated this study. The specific objectives of the study were to ascertain the influence responsiveness, empathy, assurance, tangibility and reliability on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State. The following hotels were selected from the three (3) senatorial zones of the State: Bon Hotel Awka, Cihcotel Hotel Awka and Golden Tuplip Hotel Agulu were selected for Anambra Central. Swiss Park Hotel and Suites Nnewi, Hotel De Robin Nnewi and Stone Hill Signature Hotel Ozubulu. Top Land Hotel Onitsha, Dolly Hills Hotels Onitsha and Villa Point Hotel and Suite Aguleri (Anambra North). Relevant concepts, theoretical and empirical studies were reviewed. The study was anchored on SERVQUAL model. Survey research design was employed. The population of the study comprises of the total number of past customers who had patronized the selected hotels for the study. A sample of three hundred and eight four (384) customers were drawn using Topman's formula. Data was collected using structured questionnaire. Frequency tables and percentages were adopted in presenting the data generated and multiple regression analysis was employed in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study found that tangibility, reliability, empathy, responsiveness and assurance were found to have significant positive influence on customer satisfaction in the sampled hotels. The study concludes that service quality had significant influence on customer satisfaction in hotels in Anambra State. It recommended among others that since the service quality dimensions examined can collectively affect customer satisfaction, hotel managements should devise policies and programme to help them in each of these dimensions in order to satisfy the customers' need.

Keywords: Service Quality, Responsiveness, Empathy, Assurance, Tangibility and Reliability Customer Satisfaction

INTRODUCTION

Service quality as a concept of service marketing has gained wide academic attention by different researchers with majority of the authors narrowing their works on the five dimensions of service quality proposed by Parasuraman, et al (1985) which includes responsiveness, empathy, reliability, assurance and tangibility. Ayuba and Oparah (2018) held that service quality is one of the major factors that could lead to customer satisfaction in service sectors, but service quality dimension varies in different service sectors. Customer satisfaction has been considered one of the most important constructs and one of the main goals in marketing. The term customer satisfaction is the degree to which customer feels gratified with product and service offered by organisation which is a tool for shaping customer's repurchase intention, customer loyalty, enhancing customer lifetime value, discouraging customer churn (Abdissa, 2019). Satisfaction plays a central role in marketing because it is a good predictor of purchase behaviour

(repurchase, purchase intentions, brand choice and switching behaviour) (Wael, 2015). It is known that customer satisfaction plays an important role on increasing the market share (Aydinli & Kilic 2015). Previously, marketing departments of the businesses were very enthusiastic about finding a new customer(s). One more new customer was the source of happiness for the businesses. For this reason, old customers were not served as eager as new ones. But in this age, that is loyalty concept is significantly affecting the operations of the businesses, loyal customers are much more important than the new customers (Mejías, Godoy & Piña, 2018).

From this point of view, losing one customer means not only losing one sale but losing lifelong profit which could be obtained from the concerning customer. For these reasons, business owners tend more to retain the loyal customers. On the other hand, customer can become loyal if s/he is satisfied continuously (Aydinli et al 2015). Customer satisfaction is not a part of the service of product. If it was so, the customer satisfaction would be the same each utilization of the same service. But it is possible that the same customer may get different satisfaction level at various usage times of the same service. This shows that the satisfaction is fulfilling the expectations of customers (Henaio, 2020). However, the expectations must be fulfilled after understanding the market. Of course the service quality plays very important role in this point.

Today, with increased competition, service quality has become a popular area for academic studies and has been recognized as a competitive advantage and supportive relationship with satisfied customers (Demir & Eray, 2015). Also, quality of service has become an important tool in the service industry. Castro and Paccha (2018) opined that service quality is an important concept in the service industry and is more important for financial service providers who have difficulty in showing their customers product differentiation. Moreover, several studies have been pursuing quality of service, and a number of theories and models have been developed to address this issue and highlight the importance of implementation and different dimensions. Furthermore, there are numerous definitions and measures of service quality, but there is no consensus on a single definition. Quality of service has been defined as an overall evaluation done by the customer service, while other researchers have defined the customer service as the extent to which services meet customers' needs or expectations. In addition, quality of service is defined as the degree of discrepancy between customers' normative expectations for service and their perceptions of the performance of the service. Also, Service quality is a fitness of use, conformance to requirements which focuses on customer's evaluation on the manner and outcome in which a service is delivered; or it is the difference between customer's perception on actual service performance and their expectations of firm's services (Barinotto, 2019). Service quality is a critical prerequisite for establishing, maintaining, sustaining, enhancing and satisfying relationship with valued customer. Thus, service quality is the extent to which service exceeds customer's earlier expectation thus it plays critical role to business success (Narti & Hardjono, 2020).

Service quality is the difference between the perception of the service received and expectations of customer for the service encountered in which perception and expectation are the two central elements of service quality (Ilma & Sitti, 2023). It is assumed to be good quality of service if it consistently meets and exceeds expectations of customer. The customers assess quality as high if perception of service exceeds customer's expectations; and as low when service performance does not meet expectation. As a result, getting improved understanding of attitudes of customers helps to know how customers perceive quality of service in hotels. The prime aim of delivering quality service is to satisfy customers and measuring service quality is an efficient way to know whether the services are bad or good.

Customers have become more critical and clever in selecting a brand that provides excellent service quality. Today, it is very hard to satisfy people, the demand to a satisfying service is even more challenging. When it comes to marketing, the main goal of the entire marketing strategy is to achieve customer satisfaction. Today, in our modern world, customers' expectation and perception toward product and/or service change rapidly as well as the aspects on how they achieve the satisfaction of a product and/or service. Hotels services are one of the prerequisites for economy to function effectively (Busra, 2016). In general, large cities in developing countries are highly dependent on hotel services due to influx

of visitors. Providing adequate and appropriate hotel services is a major challenge encountered in almost all cities in the world. Hotels operating in Nigeria are consequently put into lot of pressure as a of the increased competition in the industry. Various strategies are formulated to retain the customer and the key of it is to increase the service quality level. Service quality is particularly essential in services context because it provides high level of customer satisfaction, and hence it becomes a key to competitive advantage (Rita, Oliveira & Farisa, 2019). Unsatisfactory customer service leads to a drop in customer satisfaction and willingness to recommend the service to a friend.

One of the major challenges facing Hotel Service providers is to attract and retain customers support base in the hospitality environment. Interestingly, most questions raised in service quality are concerned with customer satisfaction that is why hotel customers patronize one hotel over others and the implications of their choice. In other words, hotel customers are most likely to trust hotel service providers whose service quality satisfy their basic needs, as opposed to those who dwell on their personal achievements. The effect of these challenges is that hotel service providers are no longer relying on one strategy to attract and retain customers support rather device various means to outsmart competitors. Among such strategies is the dimensions of service quality. It is not disputable that hotel service providers spend heavily on activities that promote responsiveness, empathy, assurance, tangibility and reliability. Therefore, the efficacy of service quality dimension in persuading the customers to patronize a hotel is still questioned. In the light of the above, the study examines service quality in the day to day activities which ultimately lead to customer satisfaction. Nevertheless, research in the hotel services sector in Nigeria on this relationship, particularly within Anambra State, is scant and the subject deserves further investigation, hence, the need for this research work.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. To what degree does responsiveness influence customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State?
2. How significant is the influence of empathy on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State?
3. How significant is the influence of assurance on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State?
4. How significant is the influence of tangibility on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State?
5. To what extent does reliability influence customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses stated in null form guided this study:

- Ho₁: Responsiveness has no significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.
- Ho₂: Empathy has no significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.
- Ho₃: Assurance has no significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.
- Ho₄: Tangibility has no significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.
- Ho₅: Reliability has no significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Service Quality

Service quality has been derived from the field of marketing which values human interaction between a business and its customers. It focuses on the relationship between customer expectation of a service and their perception of the quality of provision. This relationship was introduced in 1982 by Gronroos and is known as the perceived service quality. Service quality has been an elusive concept to define and measure with no general consensus among scholars on what constitutes service quality. As a result, many scholars have labeled service quality as an 'elusive' and 'indistinct' concept that is problematic to operationalize and measure (Rahim, 2016). Before we go into what service quality is all about, let conceptualize service and quality. American Society for Marketing has defined service as the activities or benefits offered for sale or offered due to its association with specific commodity. Bahadur, Aziz and Zulfiqar (2018) defined service as "any activity or benefit provided by one party to another party which is basically intangible and does not lead to any ownership.

Chang, Jang, Li and Kim (2017) defined service as perceived benefit by senses, either alone, or associated with something physical tangible and is interchangeable nor entail ownership, and mostly intangible. Gallarza-Granizo, Ruiz-Molina and Schlosser (2020) argues that services are acts, operations, and achievements or actions, therefore, services include all economic activities that their outputs are not physical products. A service is a commodity with no physical existence, usually created and consumed at the same time. Han, Zuo, Law, Chen and Zhang (2021) described a service as a process resulting in an outcome in a partly simultaneous production and consumption process. This definition points to the fact that service provision and consumption are simultaneous activities.

Murray, Elms and Curran (2019) defines services as any act or performance that one party can offer to another that is essentially intangible and does not result in the ownership or anything, it's production may not be tied to a physical product. Omar, Saadan and Seman (2015) noted that services include all economic activities whose output is not a physical product or construction, is generally consumed at the time it is produced and provides added value in forms (such as convenience, amusement, timeliness, comfort or health) that are essentially intangible concerns of its first purchaser. Palese and Usai (2018) indicated that service is time based and the outcome of a service may result in desire change in consumer or any property of the consumer.

Service Quality Dimensions

The service quality dimensions covered in this study include;

Responsiveness: Responsiveness is the degree to which customers perceive service providers' readiness to assist them promptly. Responsiveness involves the willingness to help customers. Miguel, Johisi, Jauregui-Arroyo and Rondon-Jara (2022) maintain that responsiveness is the willingness to help customers and provide prompt service, responsiveness concerns the willingness or readiness of employees to provide service. It involves timeliness of service. Silva, Macías, Tello and Delgado (2021) sees responsiveness as the ability and willingness of service providers to be always in customers' service and their ability to perform service for them when they need it. Responsiveness concerns the willingness or readiness of employees to provide service. This dimension is concerned with dealing with the customer's requests, questions and complaints promptly and attentively. A firm is known to be responsive when it communicates to its customers how long it would take to get answers or have their problems dealt with.

Empathy: Empathy is concerned with the care of service providers to customers so that they can give personal attention to customers (Rita, Oliveira & Farisa, 2019). The attributes of this dimension are: giving individual attention to customers, employees treating customers with great care, seriously prioritizing customer interests, employees understanding customer needs and comfortable operating hours (Efdison, 2021). The essence of empathy is conveying, through personalized or customized service, that the customers are unique and special and that their needs are understood. Empathetic firms have not lost touch with what it is like to be a customer of their own organization. As such, the organization

understands customers needs and makes their services accessible to their customers. In contrast, organizations that do not provide the requested individualized attention to their customers and offer, for example, operating hours convenient for the organization and not its customers, fail to demonstrate empathetic behavior (Rita, Oliveira & Farisa, 2019).

Assurance: Assurance, relates to the knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to generate trust and confidence (Narti & Hardjono, 2020). The attributes of this dimension are: the ability of employees to build customer trust, make customers feel safe when conducting transactions, employees are consistently polite and employees are able to answer customer questions (Ali & Raza, 2017). Ali and Raza (2017) define assurance as employees' knowledge and courtesy, and the ability of the organization and its employees to inspire trust and confidence. Narti and Hardjono (2020) added that competence pertains to the organization's knowledge and skills in performing the promised service and refers to how the organization's employees interact with the customer and the customer's possessions. Beni and Sapit (2022) warn that this dimension is likely to be particularly important for services that customers perceive as high risk or for services that customers feel uncertain about their ability to evaluate the outcomes.

Tangibility: Tangibles, relating to the appearance of physical facilities, equipment, and service provider personnel (Pakurár, Haddad, Nagy, Popp & Oláh, 2019). More specifically, Pakurár et al (2019) define the tangibility as the appearance of physical facilities, equipment, personnel, and written materials. The tangibles involve the firms' representatives, physical facilities, materials, and equipment as well as communication materials. The attributes of this dimension are: modern equipment, visually appealing facilities, neat and professional looking employees and materials related to visually appealing services (Han, Zuo, Law, Chen & Zhang, 2021). Tangibility provides physical representations or images of the service that customers, particularly new customers, will use to evaluate quality. Service organizations often use tangibles to enhance their image, provide continuity and signal quality to customers (Abdissa, 2019). Tangibles entail the physical evidence of the service. Tangibles involve the appearance of physical facilities, including the equipment, personnel, and communication materials. Harwina (2021) noted that tangibility is the appearance of physical facilities, equipment, personnel dress, communication materials, the seller's outward appearance, exterior design, location and accessibility, all kinds of tools that are used for providing service. Specifically, the concept explores the physical facilities of the service provider, the appearance of personnel, the tools and equipment used to provide the service including other customers in the service facility. Tangibles are used by firms to convey image and signal quality (Ali & Raza, 2017).

Reliability: Reliability refers to service provider ability to perform the promised service in a manner that it can be dependable and of a high degree of correctness and accuracy, since customer expects to have an accurate service in terms of time commitment and performance exactly as he had been promised and that he can depend on this particular service provider (Rita, Oliveira & Farisa, 2019). The service dimension of reliability measures the consistency of performance and the dependability of the service. Reliability is the service company ability to deliver promises on time. Reliability involves the ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately. In other words, reliability is the ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately, reliability involves in consistency of performance and dependability. It means that the firm performs the service right the first time. It also means that the firm honours its promises. Reliability of service designates the seller's capability to supply the promised outputs at the stated level (Ilma & Sitti, 2023). Reliability is a service quality dimension related to the knowledge, courtesy and ability of company employees to foster self-confidence and have no doubts about the company's existence (Beni & Sapit, 2022). The attributes of this dimension are: providing services as promised, reliable in handling customer service, delivering services correctly from the first time, delivering services according to the promised time and storing documents without errors (Afthanorhan, Awang, Rashid, Foziah & Ghazali, 2019).

Customer Satisfaction

Essentially, customer satisfaction is the sense that customers get when they experience service that fulfills or surpasses their expectation. Primarily in marketing, satisfaction is defined as the global evaluation of relationship fulfillment by a firm or the positively affected state resulting from the assessment of a firm's

working relationship (Pakurár et al, 2019). Satisfaction is also one of the most important elements to explain any type of relationship among participants and a consumer's fulfillment response (Silva et al, 2021). Generally, customer satisfaction is known as an outcome of service quality, which means that it is related to the quality of the products or services provided to the customer in a positive manner. The level of customer satisfaction is also believed to be enhanced, along with an increased level of perceived quality of the product or service. In particular, customer satisfaction is considered to be an intrinsic variable that explains returning customers and their post-behaviors of purchasing products and services (Barinotto, 2019).

Ali and Raza (2017) noted that customer satisfaction is an overall customer attitude towards a service provider, or an emotional reaction to the difference between what customers anticipate and what they receive, regarding the fulfillment of some need, goal or desire. Palese and Usai (2018) defined customer satisfaction as a judgment following a consumption experience-it is the consumer's judgment that a product provided (or is providing) a pleasurable level of consumption-related fulfillment. Chang, Jang, Li and Kim (2017) defined customer satisfaction as a person's feelings of pleasure or disappointment resulting from comparing a product's perceived performance (or outcome) in relation to his or her expectations. Customer satisfaction can be associated with feelings of acceptance, happiness, relief, excitement, and delight.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This research work is anchored on SERVQUAL model as developed by Parasuraman, et al (1985). SERVQUAL model is the most widely used approach to measuring service quality. It measures the customer's overall judgment of the service experience based on a number of dimensions. The SERVQUAL instrument, which identifies five service quality dimensions, is the most widely used exponent of such an approach, particularly in relation to consumer services. The five most important dimensions of service quality are: tangible aspects, e.g. facilities, appearance and equipment; assurance, e.g. knowledge, security and professional credibility; reliability, e.g. ability to perform dependably and accurately; responsiveness, e.g. willingness to help and promptness, and empathy, e.g. care, courtesy and attention as perceived. Service quality is therefore a function of pre-purchase customers' expectations, perceived process quality and perceived output quality. Parasuraman et al (1985), conceptualized service quality as the gap between customers' expectation and their perception of the service experience.

The SERVQUAL has come under some criticisms. Francis Buttle has criticized the SERVQUAL on a number of theoretical and operational bases. He noted that the five dimensions of SERVQUAL are not universals and that the model fails to draw on established economic, statistical and psychological theory (Buttle, 1996). But SERVQUAL has been used to measure service quality in a variety of contexts. The wide array of application of such an instrument as SERVQUAL spells confidence in its utilization as a technique for measuring service quality in various business sectors and service industries. In their arguments in support of the SERVQUAL, Palese and Usai (2018), posit that SERVQUAL remains the most complete attempt to conceptualize and measure service quality. They contend that its main benefit is the ability of researchers to examine numerous service industries such as healthcare, banking, financial services and education. The fact that SERVQUAL has critics does not render it moot. Rather the criticisms may well have to do with how researchers use the tool.

Until now, there has been no conclusive method for measuring service quality; however, researchers agreed that the SERVQUAL dimensions are multifaceted and were vital elements in any study of service quality (Brady & Cronin, 2001). Parasuraman et al (1985; 1988) argue that "the five dimensions used in the SERVQUAL scale represent and provide generic instrument and dimensions for measuring service quality in a variety range of services". Over the past years, the SERVQUAL instrument has been used widely and extensively for measuring service quality in different contexts and industries like banking, healthcare, hotels, restaurants retail chains, communication, real estate, higher education, etc. In addition to that, the SERVQUAL instrument has been used widely in several cultures and countries including: the USA, UK, China, Honk Kong, Greece, and so many other countries. "The SERVQUAL scale has been

imitated and appreciated well in the service quality literature in the last decades by academics, researchers and industry people” (Buttle, 1996).

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Ilma and Sitti (2023) investigated the effect of service quality on customer satisfaction using goods delivery services in Makassar City. Regression analysis was employed in analyzing the data. The results showed that tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy had a positive and significant effect on the customer satisfaction. Simultaneously all service quality variables have a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction. Miguel, Johisi, Jauregui-Arroyo and Rondon-Jara (2022) carried a study on the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction in restaurants in Los Olivos, Peru. The study is based on a quantitative and correlational research design. The study employed multiple regression technique in analyzing the data. The study found that reliability, empathy and tangibles have significant relationship with customer satisfaction. The study also found that responsiveness and safety have insignificant relationship with customer satisfaction.

Beni and Sapit (2022) investigated the influence of service quality with the dimensions of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy and tangibles on customer satisfaction. Multiple linear regression was employed in analyzing the data. The study found that reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy and tangibles have significant influence on customer satisfaction at PT. Pelindo Marine Service. The study concludes that service quality have significant influence on customer satisfaction. Abdissa (2019) carried out a study on the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction with particular reference to Nekemte Municipality, Oromia Region, Ethiopia. Correlation and multiple regressions were used to investigate the relationship between dependent and independent variables. The study found that service quality dimensions (tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy) have significant impact on customer satisfaction.

Osoimehin, Hassan and Abass (2015) examined customer’s perception of service quality in the Nigerian telecommunication sector. The data was subjected to descriptive statistics. One Sample Test statistic was employed in testing hypothesis. The results of the study revealed that there was a positive and significant relationship between service quality and both, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty, and also service quality is considered as a major factor in choosing telecommunication service provider in Nigeria. Horsu and Yeboah (2015) examined the influence of service quality on customer satisfaction. Multiple regressions analysis result proved that continuous service, comfort, affordability and reliability had a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction, with safety having positive but insignificant effect. However driver behavior had negative effect on customer satisfaction.

Melaku (2015) examined the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction in Bank of Abyssinia S.C. using SERVPERF model. The data collected from the questionnaire were analyzed using statistical tools such as mean, correlation, and regression analysis VIA SPSS Version. The results of this study indicate that, all the service quality dimensions (tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, empathy and assurance) have positive and significant relationship with customer satisfaction. Dalia, Hesham, Elham and Osman (2016) investigated the impact of key dimensions of service quality on customers’ satisfaction and loyalty using evidences from the restaurant industry in Sudan using Dineserv model. Multiple regression analysis was employed in analyzing the data. Assurance, empathy, tangibility, and reliability were the most significant dimensions of service quality that had positive influence on customer satisfaction while assurance, empathy, and tangibility were the most significant dimensions that had positive influence on customers’ loyalty.

The empirical literature reviewed revealed conflicting findings on the influence of service quality dimensions on consumer satisfaction in the hospitality sector. Similarly, majority of the scholarly work reviewed were foreign with only few local studies in the hospitality sector, hence a big knowledge gap in Nigeria particularly in Anambra State. Despite the previous extensive research work, there is evident gap in knowledge in terms of the relationship between service quality and consumer satisfaction in the hospitality sector in Anambra State, Nigeria. This study bridged this gap in knowledge. Hence, there is

paucity of local studies that focused on service quality and customer satisfaction. Consequently, this study intended to fill these gaps in literature by studying the selected independent variables of service quality and its influence on customer satisfaction. The study will improve the existing literature by providing empirical evidence on the contribution of service quality of hospitality firms in Anambra State and will fill the existing contextual and theoretical gap.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted survey research design. This study covered the three senatorial zones of Anambra State, Nigeria. The senatorial zones are Anambra Central, Anambra North and South senatorial zones. Three popular hotels from each of the senatorial zones in Anambra State were studied. Bon Hotel Awka, Cihcotel Hotel Awka and Golden Tuplip Hotel Agulu were selected for Anambra Central. Swiss Park Hotel and Suites Nnewi, Hotel De Robin Nnewi and Stone Hill Signature Hotel Ozubulu were selected for Anambra State South. Top Land Hotel Onitsha, Dolly Hills Hotels Onitsha and Villa Point Hotel and Suite Aguleri were selected for Anambra North. Only the customers of these hotels were selected for the study. Since the population of the customers of selected hotels in Anambra State is not known, the researcher employed Topman’s formula in determining the sample size of 384.

The study used structured questionnaires as data collection instrument. The data generated through questionnaires were analyzed using table and percentage analysis. Furthermore, multiple regression analysis was conducted to test the hypotheses formulated exclusively for this study. The statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 21 were employed to test the hypotheses. The regression model is stated in functional form as follows:

$$CS = f(RES, EMP, ASS, TAN, REL)$$

Where

- CS = Customer Satisfaction
- RES = Responsiveness
- EMP = Empathy
- ASS = Assurance
- TAN = Tangibility
- REL = Reliability

The regression model is restated in econometric form as follows:

$$CS = \alpha + \beta_1RES + \beta_2EMP + \beta_3ASS + \beta_4TAN + \beta_5REL + \epsilon \quad - \quad - \quad - \quad (1)$$

Where:

- Y = Dependent Variables
- α = Constant Term
- β = Beta Coefficients
- β_1 to β_4 = Independent variables
- ϵ = Error Term

RESULTS

The data generated from the respondents were presented, analyzed and interpreted in this section. A total of 384 copies of questionnaire were distributed to the customers of selected hotels out of which 376 copies were returned while 8 copies were not returned. Out of 376 copies returned, 364 were properly filled and found usable for the analysis while the remaining 10 copies were not properly filled. This gave a response rate of 94.8%.

Analysis of the Regression results

Regression analysis was used to test the hypothesized influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable and the coefficient of determination (R^2) is the most common measure that is used to predict and evaluate the predictive accuracy of a structural model. It also shows the combined effects of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The R^2 points of 0 to 1 with the higher points is an

indicative of a higher level of predictive accuracy, which explains the extent to which the variability of a factor can be caused or explained by their relationship with other factors.

ANOVA enables to examine the main effect of independent variables to dependent variable. The effect size (F^2) is an additional measure that is used to assess the R^2 for all endogenous constructs to understand the significance of their impact. It also assesses the substantive influence of the predictor construct on the dependent variable. The regression results are presented in tables below.

Table 1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.755 ^a	.571	.565	1.003	1.785

a. Predictors: (Constant), Reliability, Assurance, Tangibles, Empathy, Responsiveness

b. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

Source: SPSS Version 21.0

Table 2 ANOVA RESULT

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	478.321	6	95.664	95.111	.000 ^a
	Residual	360.083	358	1.006		
	Total	838.404	364			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Reliability, Assurance, Tangibles, Empathy, Responsiveness

b. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

Source: SPSS Version 21.0

Table 1 recorded R square (R^2) value of 0.486 indicating that reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy and responsiveness explains moderately 57.1% of the variations in customer satisfaction with selected hotels in Anambra State. The Durbin-Watson statistics value of 1.785 in table 1 showed that the variables in the model are not auto-correlated and are therefore, reliable for predictions.

The F-statistics value of 95.111 with a probability value of 0.000 in table 2 indicated that the independent variables (reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy and responsiveness) has significant collective influence on the dependent variable (customer satisfaction). This result showed that reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy and responsiveness can collectively account for the variations in customers' satisfaction with hotels in Anambra State.

Test of Hypotheses

The five hypotheses earlier formulated in chapter one were tested using the t value and probability value in the regression coefficients outcome. The table is presented below:

Table 3 Coefficient of the Regression Result

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	18.916	1.918		9.863	.000	
1	Tangibility	.123	.043	.158	2.870	.004
	Reliability	.085	.044	.202	2.923	.005
	Responsiveness	.171	.044	.209	2.901	.007
	Empathy	.076	.049	.185	2.562	.009
	Assurance	.028	.044	.204	3.632	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

Source: SPSS 21.0

Test of Hypothesis One

Ho: Responsiveness has no significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.

Hi: Responsiveness has significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.

In testing this hypothesis, the t-statistics and probability value in table 3 is used. Responsiveness has a t-statistics of 2.901 and a probability value of 0.006 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that responsiveness has significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Ho: Empathy has no significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.

Hi: Empathy has significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State. Empathy has a t-statistics of 2.562 and a probability value of 0.009 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that empathy has significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.

Test of Hypothesis Three

Ho: Assurance has no significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.

Hi: Assurance has significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State. Assurance has a t-statistics of 3.632 and a probability value of 0.009 which is statistically insignificant. Therefore, we reject the null hypotheses and accept the alternative hypothesis which states that assurance has significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.

Test of Hypothesis Four

Ho: Tangibility has no significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.

Hi: Tangibility has significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State. Tangibility has a t-statistics of 2.870 and a probability value of 0.004 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses and conclude that tangibility has significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.

Test of Hypothesis Five

Ho: Reliability has no significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.

Hi: Reliability has significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State. Reliability has a t-statistics of 2.923 and a probability value of 0.005 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that reliability has significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study investigated the influence of service quality on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State. Data were sourced from customers of selected hotels in Awka. The data generated were subjected to empirical analysis and the following were discovered. The study found that responsiveness has significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State. This implies that the hotels willingness to help customers and provide prompt service affects the level of customer satisfaction in hotels. This agrees with the findings of Ilma and Sitti (2023) that responsiveness had a positive and significant effect on the customer satisfaction. Similarly, Beni and Sapit (2022) found that responsiveness had significant influence on customer satisfaction. This disagrees with the findings of Miguel et al (2022) that responsiveness has an insignificant relationship with customer satisfaction.

The study also found that empathy has significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State. This shows that empathy displayed by the employees of the hotels especially in terms of

employees treating customers with great care and seriously prioritizing customer interests and needs affects the level of their customer satisfaction. This tally with the findings of Miguel et al (2022) empathy had significant relationship with customer satisfaction. Also, Abdissa (2019) found that empathy had significant impact on customer satisfaction. This is opposed to the findings of Juhari, Bhatti and Piaralal (2016) that empathy has no significant effect on customer loyalty.

The study also found that assurance has significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State. This indicates that the knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to generate trust and confidence can affect the level of customer satisfaction in hotels. This corresponds to the findings of Beni and Sapit (2022) found that assurance had significant influence on customer satisfaction. Similarly, Abdissa (2019) found that assurance had significant impact on customer satisfaction.

The study further found that tangibility has significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State. This shows that the appearance of physical facilities, equipment, and service provider personnel can affect the level of satisfaction derived by customers of the hotels. This agrees with the findings of Ilma and Sitti (2023) that tangibility has significant effect on customer satisfaction.

Finally, the study found that reliability has significant influence on customer satisfaction in selected hotels in Anambra State. This implies that the hotel's ability to perform the promised service in a manner that it can be dependable and of a high degree of correctness and accuracy influences the level of customer satisfaction. This is in line with the findings of Miguel et al (2022) reliability had significant relationship with customer satisfaction. But this finding disagrees with that of Koksai and Dema (2014) whose study indicates that reliability has no significant relationship with customer loyalty.

CONCLUSION

This work examined the influence of service quality on customer satisfaction in hotels in Anambra State. The study found that of all the service quality dimensions studied, tangibility, reliability, empathy, responsiveness and assurance was found to have significant positive influence on customer satisfaction in the sampled hotels. Therefore, the study concludes that service quality had significant influence on customer satisfaction in hotels in Anambra State. This conclusion is supported by significant f-statistics which measures collective significant of the effect of the explanatory variables on the dependent variable. Therefore, the service quality dimensions (tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, empathy and assurance) can collectively explain the variations in customer satisfaction in hotels in Anambra State.

This study confirmed the fivefold service quality dimensions namely, tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy in the hospitality sector in Anambra State context, proving service quality as a multidimensional construct as mentioned in the literature. The current study narrowed the empirical gap by exploring the influence of service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction. Since the offerings of the hotels are more or less similar in the competitive hospitality industry, one hotel can differentiate itself from another only through the quality of the service they deliver. Developing higher levels of service quality in the hotels leads to enhanced customer satisfaction.

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, it is recommended that the management of hotels should organize training and refresher courses for all its employees especially those that have direct contact with the customers in order to develop/improve their behaviour during encounter with customers. Since empathy was found to have significant effect on customer satisfaction, an easy accessibility of service along with prompt services will acts as an icing on the cake for customers to maintain a good relationship with the customers. The management should devise policies and programmes to will help them in each of these dimensions in order to satisfy the customers' needs as they were all found to have significant relationship with the level of customer satisfaction. Hotels should emphatically focus on the physical features and ambience of it environment so that the customers can feel pleased enough to revisit since tangibility was found to have significant relationship with customer satisfaction. Service equipments should be updated and this will help to get prompt services to customers to enhance the relationship with them. Customers may get impressed with the neat appearances of frontline employees, which further attract the customers to interact with the employees which again helps in customer satisfaction.

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